

Transformation of some Selected Pesticides

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The results of photochemical and microbial transformations of some selected pesticides, carried out in our laboratory form the subject-matter of this review article. The transformations of five herbicides viz. pendimethalin, fluchloralin, oxadiazon, oxyfluorfen and butachlor as well as two insecticides, carbofuran and hydromethylnon by microbial and photochemical means resulted in the isolation and characterisation of several interesting photo- and microbial metabolites. The structures of these transformation products were arrived at on the basis of spectroscopic evidence.

The widespread use of different synthetic organic pesticides have proliferated intensely in the biosphere and have significantly contributed to problems of environmental pollution. It is now well documented that pesticides undergo structural changes in the environment through chemical, biochemical and photochemical processes and some of these transformation products of pesticides are sometimes equally or even more toxic than the original ones, thus posing serious threats to mankind. Therefore, information on the various transformations suffered by a pesticide molecule exposed to microorganisms and physical forces (uv light) is of vital importance to those seriously concerned with questions of environmental quality and public health as well as indispensable for understanding the optimum condition of pesticide use. Moreover, the microbial habitat and physical forces such as uv light are frequently the major means by which pesticides are eliminated from a variety of ecosystem. With this objective in view, the transformations of some selected pesticides caused by microbial and photochemical means have been studied in our laboratory during the last few years, a brief account of which would form the subject-matter of the present article.

Pendimethalin

Pendimethalin [*N*-(1-ethylpropyl)-2,6-dinitro-3,4-xylylidine, **1**], a representative member of a growing

list of *N*-substituted-2,6-dinitroanilines, is a selective herbicide that controls most annual grasses and certain broad leaf weeds like cotton, soybean and others. Earlier studies¹ on the photodecomposition of **1** in soil exposed to sunlight showed much lower conversion. However, a preliminary study in our laboratory on the photodecomposition of **1** in organic solvents and Kalyani soil led to the isolation and identification of a C-dealkylated photoproduct (**2**) along with two other unknown photometabolites². Simultaneously, Dureja and Walia³ identified several photoproducts when **1** was irradiated in methanol for 48 h ($\lambda = 300-400$ nm) and this study revealed that photodecomposition involved dealkylation, nitro group reduction and cyclisation³.

Previous studies¹⁻³ on the photodecomposition of **1** in solution and adsorbed on soil probably involved indirect photochemical processes. We studied the photochemistry of **1** at its maximum uv absorption ($\lambda \geq 250$ nm). A photolysed methanolic solution upon column chromatographic fractionation followed by semipreparative hplc separation afforded five new photoproducts (**6-10**) (Chart 1) of **1** demonstrating thereby that photodecomposition of **1** involved mainly *N*-dealkylation, arylmethyl oxidation in addition to processes like nitro group elimination and cyclisation⁴.

Chart 1

Further studies on the transformation of **1** into two new photoproducts (**11** and **12**), the mechanism in presence of reactive OH radicals yielded yet of their genesis is underway⁵.

Chart 3

Fluchloralin

Fluchloralin [*N*-(2-chloroethyl)-2,6-dinitro-*N*-propyl-4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline; **16**], another member of substituted dinitroaniline class, has been introduced in India for the control of various weeds. A field study conducted during the kharif season on the persistence of **16** in soil indicated two pseudo-first order kinetics and the average half-lives varied from 5.13 to 5.22 days in the first phase and 11.23 to 11.8 days in the second phase when **16** was applied at the rate of 1.5 and 3.0 kg a.i.ha⁻¹. In a preliminary study, metabolite **17** could be detected in soil⁹ seven days after application. The details of microbial transformation of **16** by *Aspergillus*

flavus and *Fusarium solani* have been studied in our laboratory. Degradation of **16** by *A. flavus* and *F. solani* resulted in the formation of several metabolites, thirteen (**17**–**29**) of which (Chart 2) were characterised based on GC-MS data. Besides known mechanism of microbial transformation of dinitroanilines, methylation of anilino nitrogen, direct elimination of nitro group from the aromatic ring without any further ring substitution were also observed. Possible pathways of degradation of **16** in pure culture have been proposed¹⁰.

Carbofuran

Carbofuran [2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethylben-

Chart 4

zofuranyl-7-yl methylcarbamate; **30**] is a broad spectrum insecticide. In a preliminary study, 3-hydroxycarbofuran (**31**) was identified as the only photoproduct of **30** in leaf system. In our laboratory, **30** when irradiated with sunlight in different solvents furnished several photoproducts. Thirteen compounds (**31–43**) could be characterised from GC-MS data and other spectral evidence. However, two photoproducts (**31**, **32**) were confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples¹². In continuation of our investigation on the photodegradation of **30**, some more photoproducts (**44–51**) have been characterised (Chart 3) based on GC-MS data. The transformation involved hydrolysis, oxidation, methylation, chlorination and rearrangement¹³.

Hydramethylnon

Hydramethylnon [5,5-dimethylperhydropyrimidin-2-one, 4-(trifluoromethyl)-(4-(trifluoromethyl) styryl)-cinnanylidene hydrazene; **52**] is a new member of amidinohydrazone class of insecticide. During daylight hours, **52** has been found to decompose very rapidly thereby indicating its photosuscep-

tibility¹⁴. Mallipudi *et al.*¹⁵ characterised four photoproducts (**53–56**) of **52** (Chart 4) when irradiated by uv light in distilled water. We studied the effect of pH on the photodecomposition of **52**. Sunlight irradiation of **52** in aqueous media at different pH value resulted in 80–94% transformation within 10 h. The rate of disappearance of **52** was affected marginally by the initial pH of the reaction medium. After 10 h of irradiation, three products were isolated and the structures of two of these **56** and **57** were established¹⁶.

Oxadiazon

Oxadiazon [5-*tert*-butyl-3-(2,4-dichloro-5-isopropoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-(3*H*)-one; **58**] is a selective pre-emergent soil applied herbicide. Finkel'shtein *et al.*¹⁷ observed in a laboratory study that **58** persisted over a year in soil and were unable to isolate any microbial strain which could effectively utilise **58** as a sole source of carbon and nitrogen. Contrary to their observation, we could isolate *Fusarium solani* from soil cropped under paddy cultivation with no

Chart 5

previous history of **59** which degraded by co-metabolic process and eleven metabolites (**59–69**) (Chart 5) were characterised based on ir, ¹H nmr and GC-MS data. Excepting **60**, all other products are being reported for the first time as fungal metabolites and the degradation was proved to proceed via dechlorination, N-decarboxymethylation, acetylation, C-dealkylation and ring cleavage¹⁸. Moreover, five additional compounds (**70–74**) have been characterised when **59** was incubated in soil at water holding capacity¹⁹.

Oxyfluorfen

Oxyfluorfen [2-chloro- α,α,α -trifluoro-*p*-tolyl-3-ethoxy-4-nitrophenyl ether; **75**] is a new member of diphenyl ether group of herbicides. The transformation of **75** by microbial and photochemical means has been studied for the first time in our laboratory. The photolysed methanolic solution of **75** yielded thirteen (**76–88**) products²⁰, while microbial degradation²¹ of **75** resulted in the isolation of three new products (**89–91**) in addition

Chart 6

to three (**77**, **85**, **88**) previously isolated photo-products (Chart 6). The major degradative pathways of **75** involved hydrolysis of ether linkage, nitro group reduction and dechlorination²⁰.

Butachlor

Butachlor [2-chloro-2,6-diethyl-*N*-(butoxymethyl)acetanilide; **92**] is a member of α -chloroacetanilide class of herbicide. Beestman and Deming²¹ reported that microbial degradation is one of the major avenues for the degradative dissipation of **92** in soil. We extended our study to include some

more products from the transformation of **94** by *Fusarium solani* and *F. oxysporum*. Degradation of **92** by *F. solani* resulted in the formation of at least 32 metabolites which could be detected by GC-MS. Out of these, three compounds (**93–95**) (Chart 7) were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples and the structures of other nine compounds (**96–104**) were conjectured from GC-MS²².

Considering the transformation of various pesticides by microorganisms and physical forces in the laboratory to yield various transformation

Chart 7

products, it seems quite reasonable to expect these compounds to be found in soil, plant and/or water. In recent years, much attention has been focussed on the identification of transformation products. However, little is known about their toxicological significance. Although the transformation products apparently seem to be non-toxic, but there are several reports that some of the transformation/degradation products are equally or even more toxic than the parent pesticides. As a result, the transformation products need thorough toxicological evaluation for assessing the environmental hazards associated with pesticides. Therefore, monitoring of pesticides on various components of the ecosystem which is normally carried out by measuring the parent pesticide does not give the total picture. The picture is incomplete without a more detailed toxicological data about their transformation/metabolic products. Therefore, for safety regulation of pesticides, the totality of toxicants including the toxic transformation products/metabolites and their dissipation

needs to be monitored. Thus, this type of laboratory study has broad significance in formulating environmental usage and persistence parameters of pesticides.

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